

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Introduction of soft skills and importance of its implementation in growing stage of students

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Abstract

Today, everyone is rushing to get as many technical skills as possible because they think that achieving a degree is much sufficient to secure a good job in a company. Considering the outlook of majority, most of the people still follow tedious approach but at the same time there are certain companies which have started demanding soft skills to work in a multinational company or small-scale organization. So, by observing this demand many colleges and educational institutions are adapting this change and developing such skills in their students. With this review paper we have tried to project a reflection of importance which will showcase the need of the hour. This paper will help in understanding the concept that if we think just a step forward and implement these soft skills in pupil's growing stage then it will create a better society and a career as well. It will also help in rejuvenating behavioural skills of current generation.

Keywords: Soft Skills; Technical Skills; Behavioural Skills; Career; Education

1. Introduction

The education system as well as the market strategies are changing rapidly back when people with excellent academic records with combination of good working experience were entreat by maximum of the business institution but in present era cognitive capability and experience are not satisfactory for the entrance and hike in the business world. At this present time, only those candidates who are inventive and self-directed with excellent communication Skills are employed and motivated by the employers. This is one of the main reasons of less hiring by corporate.

Despite of such great importance of interpersonal skills, most of the schools/colleges/institutions are unenthusiastic to introduce soft skills/interpersonal skills training in the curriculum of their school/college. The academic structure in the present era is changing by leaps and bonds. In this present scenario no matter how well versed a person think he is with regards to the hard skills/technical skills he will not be succeeded in the corporate world if you are unable to interact/communicate with your teammate or clients.

It is always experienced that the faculty as well as the management of any institution/college stands with a lengthy standing accusation against the newcomers that they lack soft skills/interpersonal skills due to which they are unemployable. Talking about the academic institutions, they refuse to take any responsibility and so the entire onus goes over to the guardians to train soft skills in their wards. All this fuss creates turmoil where each one tries to hold the other responsible and, in the end, students are the ones who deteriorate. [1] [2] [3] [4]

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2. Knowledge of soft skills in growing stage. [5][6][7]

2.1. What does soft skill actually mean?

This is a vexed question and need to shed light on before we move further. The frequent changing approach regarding “what is soft skill” is the reason behind why this question is burdensome to answer. Sometimes people come across such situation under which one topic comes under soft skills in one subject and on the same very side the same topic falls under the category of hard skills in another subject. In addition to this commotion soft skills differ from place to place, culture to culture region to region and hierarchy to hierarchy.

In this high-tech age, cultivating soft skill in students can provide them an edge and case work as a support system in achieving success in their professional lives.

2.2. Why should school have this responsibility?

Life skills being overnice, includes the flourishing of personality and most of the time acquired experientially as certain situations come across the growing child. This is the need of the hour that various of the situation are ‘created’ in the school far the child so that he gets chance to learn these life skills. This is important as school is the child’s second home.

Depending upon the current scenario educational and training organizations must train their students in such a way that they should be capable enough to face the future market to stand as managers, entrepreneurs, leaders and many more. Here are few soft skills students must hold today.[8]

2.2.1. Problem solving

The skill of problem solving will help one in managing any circumstances that may arise many difficulties. This skill strengthens one to withstand in any of the situation and come up with its solution. Keeping the current situation in mind one should work over his problem-solving skills as we are the part of an unexpected world, where any kind of situation may turn into an adverse one. This is the reason why students should be prepared to overcome circumstances problems in their growing stage itself.

2.2.2. Innovative/creative thinking

We always see students as the future of our society so it is very important that they possess a creative approach in their every aspect of life. This creative approach will help them in understanding the high society in a better way and with that they may end up with such outcome that might provide the rest of the society a new outlook.

2.2.3. Teamwork

Although all the skills listed above or will be discussed further are important for students to cultivate in their lives but with that, teamwork is one of the most expected skill that every student must develop in themselves as it will help them wherever they may go. The productivity standards can only be achieved by working together in a team. The significance of unity is something that every student must understand. To achieve a big task, it is important for people to work together and with that many times they will have to comfort each other.

2.2.4. Decision making

Right from the initial stage of the career students must acquire the capability to make decisions within the provided time frame. By this they no longer be dependent on others and can take their own stand in life. The people they select as friends or the groups they get associated with also support them, develop their personality. Even there, decision making plays important role.

2.2.5. Intrapersonal skills

The intra personal skill is one of that skill upon which rest of all soft skills are based, in other words we can say that intra personal skills are the master skill because they deal in understanding oneself, one’s emotional intelligence, strength, weakness, thought process, beliefs and one’s perception on things. These skills help one in developing flexible nature and frame oneself into a better leader with sufficient knowledge about oneself. A person with these skills is

capable of taking his own stand on many decisions. These skills are also important because once a person is able to understand himself than only, he can corelate with other's situation and can understand it in a better manner.

2.2.6. Interpersonal skills

Just after acquiring capability of understand one. People start grasping the way of others working. Skills that provide one the potential of understanding the brain power and conduct of their co-workers/colleagues are termed as interpersonal skills. Students from their initial stage of learning must acquire this skill as it can help them working in a team. With these skills they can learn others reaction over different situation by which they can accordingly put forward their ideas and that will be their advantage.

2.2.7. Communication Skills

Sometimes self-analysis is much easier than making others understand our perspective. The communication skills are the one that holds the power to bridge the gap between mankind. This is a principal skill that everyone should inculcate to communicate. One should have the potential of dealing with all temperament people whether argumentative or empathetic. This is a skill that everyone must possess be it a student or a working professional. For students this may turn very helpful if they manage to cultivate communication skills rightly at correct time as it will be beneficial for them in all the sphere of life.

2.2.8. Leadership Skills.

Every student once in his life faces a phrase where he gets a chance to take an important decision for himself/ herself. Whether they choose to be a follower or a leader. These are the chances that may arise at any point in the form of class election, representative selection, or student union election and that will decide whom the majority wants and thinks can be a leader. With these respective qualities of making wise and right decisions, harmonize with other people, carry off an event trouble free can forefront as a leader. Leadership is one of that important skills that every student may use further in their career.

2.2.9. Positive Attitude.

If we talk about today's scenario where each individual leads a hectic lifestyle which has all the way changed each person's approach into a negative factor. Keeping this in mind one should be capable of acquiring place in others heart with positive approach. When we talk about academics whether it be a student or a teacher each would want to get someone with that approach which can drive educational year with positive attitude. For the maintenance of friendly environment at any academic institutions, it becomes the utmost responsibility of all the students to inculcate skill of positive attitude in themselves. The surrounding in which students grow, plays a very important role in deciding what kind of attitude they will develop. We should make sure they receive an environment where they can develop positive attitude. So, this responsibility of creating a positive atmosphere around to the students where they get the chance to grow with positive approach lies over the shoulder of parents and teachers.

2.2.10. Listening Skills.

The fact is if one wants to be a good speaker, he has to be a good listener first. The art of listening lets a person express himself better in front of others with that it also allows one to understand what the other person is trying to say. For a student it is very much important to develop the art of listening in themselves as active listening encourage sensible thinking that can help in bringing down the anxiety and can even be helpful in de-stressing the students. This skill should be the priority for every student and each one should possess it as this can be very beneficial specially when one is trying to Chase his dreams and want to flourish with bright future.

3. Benefits of training at young age- Biologically it has been found that human goes with the maximum brain development at the age range of 12 to 18. As per a study of applied education systems they have prepared a module of few soft skills which are very beneficial for school students and will also help them to gain these skills in a better way to lead towards a future with great human values. A list given below contains certain soft skills. [9]

- Social skills
- Empathy
- Patience
- Public speaking
- Time management
- Customer service

- Project management
- Leadership
- Emotional intelligence
- Critical thinking

As per a study of American society of community colleges they have collected a data on percentage of skills generally HR is looking these days because at the end what matter is a career with a good educational background. With the help of clustered column, we have tried to portray a compiled data. It will help students to understand the future scenario of learning these soft skills.

This chart explains about today's need of employers which is affecting the employment status of our country

Benefits of providing training of these soft skills to students is undoubtedly a result-oriented process and here are few benefits mentioned below.[10] [11]

- Boost up the brain productivity
- Improve behaviour
- Enhance the public dealing activities
- Increase the self-confidence to perform
- Students become more focused
- Building up the risk-taking abilities
- Students attain innovative and problem-solving attitude

4. Conclusion

After observing the current scenario we have seen that soft skills are most important aspect of professional life and people are getting trained in it so if students can be trained in this domain at a small age then it will not be a tough situation for them in future. To obtain any designation in some organization we must have these soft skills. This implementation should be done at school level first of all and for that teachers should be trained in this. So, if we need a drastic change in society then this modification can lead towards a better society with raised human values.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declared no conflicts of interest

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Author's Short Biography

	<p>Vinay Kumar Pandey is a PhD Scholar at Department of Bioengineering, Integral University, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India. He has many years of teaching and training experience. After completion of his graduation in engineering from Chennai, he attended huge number of interviews at many corporate, educational organizations and defense services. He set his foot in training field while pursuing his Masters in Engineering. He is certified in Developing soft skills & personality and also in Emotional Intelligence. He takes motivational and training sessions for final year students from various educational backgrounds like MBA, MCA, M.Tech, B.Tech and others.</p>
	<p>Aanchal Anand is designated as Assistant Professor at Axis Colleges, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India. She has done her masters and experienced in taking soft skill training sessions. She is certified in Enhancing soft skills and personality. She has worked in many academic institutions at Delhi and Kanpur. She is specialized in grammar, spoken English and various personality development activities. She has contributed in this field by creating many innovative and useful activities which help students in understanding soft skills with keen interest. Her positive attitude towards any problem is really appreciating and it reflects her problem-solving skills positively.</p>